

ONLINE TRAINING ON FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: The article explores the topic of protection, which is important for modern society students from coronavirus infection. The author suggests specific ways educational and upbringing in the format of discussion communication, exercises, phonetic song workouts, independent pre-discussion works using computer technology. Listed special pedagogical conditions conducive to a benevolent cooperation and new understanding of the problem.

Key words: online training, protection, discourse-discussion approach, internal motive, discussion, cooperation.

The modern period of self-isolation determines the need formation of an active position of students to remove the fear of unknown, stimulates to solve difficult problems. In connection with situations occurring in public life related to coronavirus infection, educational technologies acquire a new format, including the development of the ability to withstand difficulties, find a way out of crisis situations, exercise control over your activities and behavior.

Practical online classes showed the development of new experiences interaction, the development of creative thinking, the opportunity self-improvement, acceptance of moral norms and rules of joint activities. The basis of the new pedagogical methodology was taken the author's theory of the discourse-discussion approach to the content educational process.

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages under discourse mean not only the product of speech activity but also the process of its creation, which is determined by extralinguistic factors, i.e. communicative context and conditions of

communication. In the context of identifying internal motivation is taken into account the concept of "discourse" as "cognitive the process associated with real speech production".

The discourse is adequate acquired knowledge, skills, cultural environment, social characteristics and student motivation. Therefore, the strategy for identifying internal discourse as intrinsic motivation implies the manifestation of the attitude of the learner to the future profession [1], [2].

Having understood the interest and inner motive of the student, the teacher can only manage and direct his activities, taking into account the key criterion in the training of professionals - integration into a new reality that feels the need for mutual learning, collective thought activity, a communication process in which teacher and students discuss problems with the use of modern information technologies.

It is possible to extract "internal motives from the depths of human consciousness only through the structure of linguistic formations". Analysis of practical lessons showed that to objectify and develop interests and aspirations, including the ability to competently, fluently and convincingly solve problems on two or more languages can be done through the educational discussion-discursive model. "Discussion (from Lat. Discussion - consideration) is discussion of any controversial issue or problem with the purpose achieving a mutually acceptable solution. Discussion promotes development the ability to correctly conduct polemics, observing the norms of ethics, affirming their position, arguing their understanding and refuting the arguments of the other parties".

According to G.V. Forties, discussion as a brainstorming discussion may have a different character depending on the studied process, the level of its problematic nature and, as a consequence, the statements made [3].

It is the discussion interaction that has all the properties conducive to identifying the stock of knowledge and abilities etc. comprises the following strategic factors:

- discursive function;

- productive and receptive speech activity;
- cognitive strategy;
- interpersonal and conceptual interaction.

In discussion communication, the highest gift of thinking is manifested activities. Special topics allow you to identify interests and develop the skills and discipline of the maximum need to know and learn, overcoming difficulties. Revealing internal motives is based on active and interested cooperation between the teacher and students, the desire to reveal hidden abilities by means of complicated in the conceptual sense of the discussion topics. Online classes show special mental actions of the student based on a high level awareness that creates a huge pool of resources that, thanks to excellent memory are realized immediately.

Students are offered the following topics: "Professionalism is the requirement of time or the necessary striving for success?", "Acquisition of knowledge - intellectual pleasure or social necessity? ", " Knowledge of foreign languages is a way to get good job or optional academic discipline? ", " Good work - high income in a routine enterprise or opportunity experiment and bring new ideas to life? "

Educational technologies of online communication involve implementation of the following functions:

- varying the thematic content of the upbringing and educational direction;
- formation of skills and abilities of independent work (drawing up business letters,
- thematic discussion programs, planning scenarios for educational discussions);
- development of skills in conflict resolution;
- training in non-conflict discourse;
- independent control of the acquired knowledge;

- focus on mastering English as a means professional communication;
- striving for continuous improvement of knowledge and skills, to learning another foreign language;
- generation of argumentation and exploratory search for a solution problems;

The presence of problem situations that contribute to the development creative and critical thinking and skills of a civilized argumentation [4].

Thus, a humane pedagogical technology containing discussion and argumentative way in online classes, helps students to continue their education and protect themselves from the coronavirus infections.

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